

MultiBypass Surgical Action Triplet Challenge 2026:

Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

MultiBypass Surgical Action Triplet Challenge 2026

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

MultiBypassT40

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Surgical workflow analysis has evolved in the types of intraoperative signals analyzed, with the goal of providing context-aware decision support to improve patient outcomes, identify surgical events, and support preoperative planning and postoperative analysis. Recent work has expanded analysis from coarse-grained levels (phases, steps) to fine-grained levels (action triplets). Action triplets describe a surgical scene using a triplet of instrument, verb, and target. To highlight the importance of surgical action triplets, recent endoscopic datasets from laparoscopic cholecystectomy procedures, such as CholecT50, have provided frame-level annotations of triplet classes. This dataset has been part of two successful sub-challenges under the EndoVis challenge.

However, with the advent of foundation models and the increasing need for model generalization across multiple centers, current surgical action triplet datasets face limitations in generalization assessment. CholecT50, while widely used, is monocentric with lower interaction density compared to multi-bypass procedures, which involve more instruments and actions, contributing to greater density and variability in instrument-anatomy interactions. Multi-institutional datasets such as ProstaTD exist but have limited test set representation per center (typically 1-2 videos). Additionally, existing test sets are relatively small in scale. To address these gaps, we introduce MultiBypassT40, a large multi-centric dataset for complex Roux-en-Y gastric bypass surgery labeled with surgical action triplets. The dataset comprises 40 videos across 4 centers, with two centers providing training, validation, and test data, and two additional centers exclusively for testing. Our test set is approximately 5x larger than existing datasets, with a substantial hidden test set distributed across three centers for robust generalization evaluation. Roux-en-Y gastric bypass procedures are, on average, longer than cholecystectomy procedures, presenting additional challenges for temporal modeling and action recognition.

This challenge focuses on developing deep learning methods for online surgical triplet recognition from surgical videos. Participants will compete with algorithms to recognize action triplets directly from the provided videos. This challenge investigates the state-of-the-art in surgical fine-grained activity recognition and establishes a new research direction focused on generalization across multiple centers.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Surgical activity recognition, action triplet, tool-tissue interaction, MultiBypassT40, deep learning, laparoscopic video analysis

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

This challenge introduces MultiBypassT40, a multi-centric surgical action triplet dataset for gastric bypass procedures that addresses three key dimensions: generalization across multiple centers with substantial test data including a hidden test set distributed across institutions, dense instrument-anatomy interactions with greater variability, and temporal modeling of extended surgical procedures. It advances beyond existing monocentric cholecystectomy datasets by providing a more comprehensive evaluation framework for surgical action triplet recognition.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The task is online surgical action triplet recognition, where the model provides triplet predictions for a current surgical frame and optionally uses context strictly from the previous frames. No access to future frames will be allowed for evaluation.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

1 hour

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We expect approximately 15 participants, based on 20 participants in the 2021 CholecTriplet sub-challenge and 10 in the 2022 version.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes, team submissions along with detailed analysis on the model results will be used for a potential publication in Medical Image Analysis journal.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

No

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team (miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The challenge will be organized as part of thematic event in conjunction with EndoVis, we will coordinate with EndoVis team for the use of the technical equipment. We will ensure that any specific additional requirements (like projector, HDMI connectivity, speakers and 2-3 wireless microphones) are communicated in advance if needed.

TASK 1: Surgical Action Triplet Recognition

SUMMARY

Abstract

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Surgical workflow analysis has evolved in the types of intraoperative signals analyzed, with the goal of providing context-aware decision support to improve patient outcomes, identify surgical events, and support preoperative planning and postoperative analysis. Recent work has expanded analysis from coarse-grained levels (phases, steps) to fine-grained levels (action triplets). Action triplets describe a surgical scene using a triplet of instrument, verb, and target. To highlight the importance of surgical action triplets, recent endoscopic datasets from laparoscopic cholecystectomy procedures, such as CholecT50, have provided frame-level annotations of triplet classes. This dataset has been part of two successful sub-challenges under the EndoVis challenge.

However, with the advent of foundation models and the increasing need for model generalization across multiple centers, current surgical action triplet datasets face limitations in generalization assessment. CholecT50, while widely used, is monocentric with lower interaction density compared to multi-bypass procedures, which involve more instruments and actions, contributing to greater density and variability in instrument-anatomy interactions. Multi-institutional datasets such as ProstaTD exist but have limited test set representation per center (typically 1-2 videos). Additionally, existing test sets are relatively small in scale. To address these gaps, we introduce MultiBypassT40, a large multi-centric dataset for complex Roux-en-Y gastric bypass surgery labeled with surgical action triplets. The dataset comprises 40 videos across 4 centers, with two centers providing training, validation, and test data, and two additional centers exclusively for testing. Our test set is approximately 5x larger than existing datasets, with a substantial hidden test set distributed across three centers for robust generalization evaluation. Roux-en-Y gastric bypass procedures are, on average, longer than cholecystectomy procedures, presenting additional challenges for temporal modeling and action recognition.

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Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

surgical action triplets, surgical workflow analysis, surgical scene understanding

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Saurav Sharma [1,2]

Lorenzo Arboit [1,2]

Lalith Sharan [1,2]

Shi Li [1,2]

Julia Alekseenko [1,2]

Joël Lavanchy [3]

Nicolas Padoy [1,2]

1 University of Strasbourg, CNRS, INSERM, ICube, UMR7357, France

2 IHU Strasbourg

3 University Digestive Health Care Center - Clarunis, University Hospital of Basel, Basel, Switzerland

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

ssharma@unistra.fr

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Lorenzo Arboit: annotation protocol development, data harmonization, challenge website design

Joël L. Lavanchy: data collection, annotation protocol development, annotation mediation and annotation supervision

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

Similar to our previous Triplet challenges, the challenge will be managed internally by the organizing team. Participants will submit Docker containers via a secure institutional submission platform (e.g., Seafiler or equivalent server), and evaluation will be conducted locally by the organizers.

c) Do you agree that your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly,

your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

https://camma-public.github.io/mbt40_challenge/

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Fully Automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants are allowed to use publicly available datasets (e.g., CholecT50, ProstaTD) along with the challenge training data that will be released during challenge launch.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

Participants from the organizers' institutes will not be permitted to submit to the official challenge leaderboard. To ensure transparency and avoid conflicts of interest, we will provide a single baseline result from our team for reference purposes only, clearly marked as non-competitive.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The winner of the challenge will be awarded a prize, if at least 3 teams submit a result for the task. Then, depending on the number of teams in the challenge, a maximum of 2 runner-ups can also be awarded a prize.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The results of all teams will be first presented in conjunction with the Endoscopic Vision Challenge meeting at MICCAI 2026. Afterwards, the information will be made available to all participating teams. The results will be made publicly available in the form of a joint publication.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Depending on the number of submissions, the top-N performing teams will be invited to co-author the joint challenge publication. Each selected team may nominate up to three qualifying authors. The order of authors in the joint publication will be determined by the challenge organizers.

Participants may publish their individual results separately only after the joint challenge paper has been published (anticipated by the end of 2026). All participating teams and institutions will be acknowledged in the joint publication.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Participating team will submit their Docker containers via a secure institutional submission link (e.g., Seafile/S3/Dropbox server). The details of the submission guidelines, including a Docker template with defined input/output protocols, will be provided on the website after rebuttal.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Evaluation metrics will be provided for participants to evaluate their algorithms on their chosen validation data split. During the validation phase, participants will conduct self-evaluation on the validation data using their docker image for sanity checks. The docker image will not be submitted to the challenge organizers at this stage. Participants will submit the output of their validated docker image to confirm that their development method follows the submission guidelines. Formats and guides for self-validation will be provided. During the final submission stage, participants will submit their final docker image for evaluation. Only the last submission from each team before the deadline will be evaluated for the challenge ranking.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

April 1st: Registration Opens

April 8th: Release of the training dataset and the script for the evaluation metrics

May 4th: Launch of discord channel for interaction with participants and colab tutorial

Jun 1st: Release of docker submission template

Jun 18th: Self-validation phase for testing docker containers

Jun 25th: Registration Closes

Jul 18th: Submission of self-validation report deadline

Sep 3rd: Docker, Presentation & Report Submission deadline (11:59pm CET)

Oct 4th/8th: Challenge Day

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

As the data consists of anonymized laparoscopic videos (i.e. no meta data identifying patient or surgical staff member is contained and all frames depicting something outside the abdominal cavity have been removed) no ethics approval is required.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The scripts for computing evaluation metrics will be provided as part of the starter kit at the time of the training dataset release.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

To participate in the challenge, each team has to submit a docker image capable of producing results on the testing examples.. Each team can choose to provide their source code, though they are not required to. Only a word-doc/pdf describing their method is required that will be used for the joint publication.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Awards for the challenge will most likely be sponsored by IHU Strasbourg. We will provide details of the sponsorship two months before the conference. Only the organizers of the challenge will have access to the labels of the test set.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research, Decision support, Additional Objectives: Surgical Workflow Analysis, Surgical action recognition, Multi-centric action analysis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration

- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification, Surgical action triplet recognition

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Patients undergoing Roux-en-Y gastric bypass surgery

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Patients undergoing Roux-en-Y gastric bypass surgery at

1. University Hospital of Strasbourg, France
2. Bern University Hospital, Bern, Switzerland
3. University Digestive Health Care Center - Clarunis, University Hospital of Basel, Basel, Switzerland
4. University Hospital of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Standard laparoscopic imaging system capturing video at 25fps

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

RGB Video extracted into frames at 1fps

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Videos from Roux-en-Y gastric bypass surgery where abdomen is shown in the laparoscopic video data.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Recognition of surgical action triplets (<instrument,verb,target>) in Roux-en-Y gastric bypass surgery across multiple centers

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Precision,Sensitivity,Description: Surgical action triplet recognition: algorithm with high average precision. From the predicted action triplet labels, the evaluation software will be able to extract and assess also the average precisions for the correct triplet's components (such as instrument, verb, target, instrument-verb, instrument-target, etc.).

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Video recordings of Roux-en-Y gastric bypass surgery at following centers

1. University Hospital of Strasbourg, France
2. Bern University Hospital, Bern, Switzerland
3. University Digestive Health Care Center - Clarunis, University Hospital of Basel, Basel, Switzerland
4. University Hospital of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Patients that underwent Roux-en-Y gastric bypass surgery were identified from institutional databases. Clinical metadata as age, sex, body-mass-index, date and duration of the operation, and outcome data as hospital length of stay and postoperative complications were retrospectively collected from the electronic health records. Video data was retrospectively collected from the respective institutional repositories. The institutional review boards approved the study and waived the need for informed consent (#2021-01666). The metadata will not be part of the challenge and will be kept private.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Total of four following centers were selected for collecting video recordings

C1. University Hospital of Strasbourg, France

C2. Bern University Hospital, Bern, Switzerland

C3. University Digestive Health Care Center - Clarunis, University Hospital of Basel, Basel, Switzerland

C4. University Hospital of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Surgeons

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case is a single laparoscopic intervention. A video of the entire operation will be provided for each case. Each case has an action triplet annotation (85 classes, each frame has a 1D binary vector, each entry indicating if the corresponding action is being performed (1) or not (0)). Additionally, each case is also provided with supplementary annotations for: Instruments, verbs and targets. All the supplementary annotations follow the same format as the triplet annotation case. Both training and testing cases are annotated with the same parameter.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The dataset consists of 16 training videos and 9 test videos from two centers C1 and C2. We additionally keep 15 videos as a hidden test set from three centers C1, C3, C4, two of which are never observed a priori (during training). The cases are provided as videos, allowing participants to exploit temporal information, but processing must be strictly causal. Participants may split the training videos into validation sets on their own. On average, a video contains 5.23K frames.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

Training, test and hidden test videos are all 100% annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The number of cases were preselected based on MultiBypass140 (fold 0). From centers C1 and C2, we annotated 5 videos each per center for training, validation, and test sets (30 videos total). To strengthen generalization assessment, we included centers C3 and C4 with 5 test videos each (10 videos total), bringing the dataset to 40 videos. Of these 40 videos, 5 videos each from C1, C3, and C4 (15 videos total) were reserved as a hidden test set

for further generalization assessment. For the remaining 25 videos, we split into 16 training and 9 test videos. The dataset size reflects the available annotation resources.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The distribution of classes in the data follows the real-world distribution.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The 15 hidden test videos (37.5% of total videos) are unseen, unpublished data. The remaining videos are public, but their triplet annotations are unseen and unpublished.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Four clinicians (two med students and two residents) annotated the data. First clinician annotated 15 videos, second 8, third 10, and fourth 7. Wherever there is an ambiguity in the label, mediation is provided by a another expert clinician.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Surgeons were given a list of items to annotate and were also educated on the use of the annotation software. We created an annotation protocol based on comprehensive study of the cases which shall kept as private. To harmonize the labels, we conducted regular meetings to discuss annotation consistency and potential edge cases with the annotaters. Furthermore, post annotation of a video, we randomly checked few labels for correctness.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Surgical experts involved in both clinical practice and surgical data science research carried out the annotation. Two medical students and two surgical residents were fully trained on surgical triplet annotations following the protocol and review process. Supervision was provided by a clinical expert in surgical data science and mediation by an expert surgeon.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Disagreements between annotators are solved through mediation by an expert surgeon. We conducted regular meetings for annotation review and additionally setup a discord channel for constant feedback on the annotations or any potential edge cases.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The frames of a video outside of abdomen and defined by the transition through the camera trocar are marked as out of body and assigned a black frame to deidentify the videos.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Potential sources of error:

1. The beginning and end of a triplet might have disagreement (1-2 seconds). The triplet annotations are performed at a temporal level, where a triplet action starts few seconds before the actual interaction (e.g. grasper grasping stomach) occurs. The initial few seconds might cause disagreement of 1-2 seconds.
2. The verb semantics might have disagreement (1-2 classes).
3. Possible classes that are underrepresented (3-5 out of 85 classes)

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Mean Average Precision (mAP) along with macro F1-score will be used to assess triplet recognition performance and perform team ranking. mAP will be computed following the ivtmetrics protocol used in the CholecTriplet2021 and CholecTriplet2022 challenges. In addition, we will report macro F1-score as a complementary metric. We will also include targeted analysis on rare triplets and provide phase-wise performance breakdowns to improve clinical interpretability.

As in prior Triplet challenges, the primary evaluation will be performed at the full Instrument-Verb-Target (IVT) level for both AP and F1-score. AP will be computed per triplet category within each video, averaged across videos to obtain category-wise AP, and then macro-averaged across categories to obtain the final mAP. Component-wise performance (Instrument, Verb, Target) will be derived from IVT predictions for interpretability.

Macro F1-score will follow the same hierarchical aggregation: F1 will be computed per triplet category within each video, averaged across videos to obtain category-wise F1, and then macro-averaged across categories to obtain the final macro F1-score.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

mAP has been established as a standard and robust metric for multi-label classification tasks, particularly compared to accuracy in the presence of long-tail class distributions. Furthermore, by combining mAP with macro-F1 for team ranking, we can evaluate how well both common and rare triplets are identified while accounting for false positives and false negatives.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

The triplet mAP and F1-score will be used to quantify model performance and submissions from the participants will be ranked in descending order based on (triplet mAP + F1-score).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Submissions with missing results on test cases are strictly prohibited.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Ranking based on triplet mAP and F1-Score is based on the task complexity, robustness across action classes, and the clinical relevance.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Statistical analysis will be performed at the video (case) level, treating each surgical recording as an independent unit. Performance metrics (macro mAP and macro F1-score) will be computed per video and aggregated across cases. Method comparisons will use the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, a non-parametric paired test suitable for small sample sizes and non-Gaussian distributions. In addition, case-level bootstrapping will be used to assess uncertainty and ranking robustness.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Precision of the performance estimates will be quantified using case-level percentile bootstrapping. Test videos will be resampled with replacement (e.g., 1,000 iterations), and the performance metrics (e.g., mAP and macro-F1) will be recomputed for each resample. 95% confidence intervals will then be derived from the resulting bootstrap distributions.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across test cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Performance variability across cases will be assessed by analyzing per-video metric distributions. Variability will be summarized using standard deviation (SD) and interquartile range (IQR) across test cases, and distributions may be visualized to identify dispersion and potential outliers.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking variability will be assessed via case-level bootstrapping. Rankings will be recomputed across bootstrap resamples, and rank stability will be summarized by reporting confidence intervals or rank frequencies.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Statistical significance between algorithms will be assessed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, a non-parametric paired test suitable when normality cannot be assumed and outliers may be present. For each pair of methods, the null hypothesis states that the median difference in performance across test cases is zero. Resulting p-values will be used to determine statistical significance, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered significant.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Missing data will not occur, as submissions will only be accepted if predictions are generated for all test cases.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Python based framework specifically torchmetrics/scikit-learn

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

For the joint challenge paper, combining algorithms strengths and/or model ensemble may be evaluated. Furthermore future direction of further works will be proposed following the algorithms strengths and weaknesses.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

The first publication on the data is expected by April, 2026

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

Based on the recommendation from the satellite event committee, we have coordinated with the EndoVis organizers to organise our challenge as a sub challenge under EndoVis as part of the thematic event.